

Connection Between Debriefing and Culture of Safety in the Operating Room

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Background

- Lack of effective communication can cause adverse events in the operating room (OR)
- Surgical safety checklists (SSC) assist with decreasing errors and improving teamwork and communication & debriefing is an essential element of the SSC
- Even with knowledge of why debriefing is important, inconsistencies in debriefing practices exist
- A standardized process for debriefing based on staff input can improve commitment to performing debriefings
- LOCAL CONTEXT: Inconsistent performance of debriefing procedures at a Southern California hospital 12-suite surgical unit was identified as a safety concern

Purpose

- This project aimed to identify barriers to proper debriefing in order to plan future improvements in the debriefing process

Methods

- Staff surveys
- Safety Attitudes Questionnaire (SAQ) measured attitudes and beliefs about the aspects of safe practice that are important to the surgical team
- Confidence Scale (C-Scale) assessed the self-efficacy of staff in performing debriefings

Conceptual Framework

A blended conceptual framework served as a lens for analysis

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based

Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change (TTM)

Model Synthesis

Identification of triggers leading to the purpose followed by creating the team and assembly of EBP identified in the literature results in a pilot But is the team ready for change? If not, identify what stage of change they are at within the TTM and adjust the pilot to facilitate the next stage of change until action can occur that results in adoption of the new EBP

Results

- Only 45.24% of staff "strongly agreed" that debriefings were common in the OR
- Responses to C-Scale questions ranged from 44% to 64%. Staff indicated lack of certainty in correct performance of the debriefing process
- These results point to lack of awareness for staff of the link between less than absolute confidence in their performance and how debriefing is part of a culture of safety
- Demographic data revealed an OR staff of 61.7% having 11 or more years of experience
- C-Scale responses showed staff were not absolutely certain they were performing debriefings correctly

Discussion

- A big revelation was the disconnect between staff perceptions about culture of safety and debriefing performance in the OR
- Unexpected results created the need for an alternate focus on linking the culture to practices, prioritizing debriefing, prior to implementation of a new standardized procedure for debriefing
- In addition, future efforts need to address staff lack of recognition that a poor culture of safety existed (failure to use debriefing)

WHO Surgical Safety Checklist

SAQ Question #4

Debriefings are common in the OR
Only 19 out of 42 staff strongly agree

